

Mapping Inequality in the Academic Research Ecosystem: A Systematic Literature Review

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Acknowledgements

I am greatly thankful to the help I received from Signe Bovard Urup and Karen Kjølby Eika in screening and coding the literature used in this article. I also wish to thank my supervisors, Professor Mads P. Sørensen and Professor Carter Bloch, for their guidance and critique in the making of this article.

Abstract

Inequality in the academic research ecosystem is a ubiquitous, persistent phenomenon and recent tendencies indicate that it is rising. There is, however, no clear overview on how inequality is conceptualised and studied. In this systematic literature review, I provide a novel framework and approach that encompasses all possible types of inequalities across the academic research ecosystem. Based on an initial screening of 4,890 articles, I identify 224 studies published between 1982 and early 2025, representing all disciplines of academia. I identify 22 conceptual themes of inequality which are highly interconnected, emphasising the multidimensionality and complexity of the concept. I also analyse temporal trends, revealing a recent, sharp increase in publications. Further examination of the literature shows a strong dominance of Global North authorship and focus, and a widespread use of quantitative methods – especially bibliometrics. Additionally, the literature’s use of theoretical frameworks and explanatory models is examined and I find that theoretical engagement is generally sparse. Similarly, the literature only to a limited degree address structural drivers and effects of inequality on the research ecosystem. Based on these findings, I end the review with a discussion that synthesises the findings and proposes a consolidated framework to support future research.

Key words: inequality; academic research ecosystem; academia; research; systematic literature review

1. Introduction

Inequality in the academic research ecosystem is a long-recognised and persistent issue. As early as 1926, Lotka observed a skewness in the distribution of scientific productivity, measured by the number of publications per author. The Matthew effect (Merton, 1968; Zuckerman, 1977) became a popular way of explaining how resources and recognition tend to concentrate around established researchers. Others, like Cole and Cole (1973) and Bourdieu (1988), emphasised how structural factors drive inequalities in research.

Contemporary research suggests these inequalities not only persist but may be intensifying. Studies show that citation shares (Nielsen & Andersen, 2021) and research funding (Katz & Matter, 2020) are increasingly concentrated to a small stratum of elite scientists. A similar pattern is apparent in the publication process where a select few commercial publishers exercise oligopolistic control (BRCP, 2022). On an institutional level, Ma et al. (2015) demonstrate how elite universities attract more funding and form cliquish networks, while the academic global North/South relationship continue to be subject to issues of structural hegemony.

Yet, despite its persistence and scope, there is no clear overview of how inequality is conceptualised and studied. This leaves the field fragmented, lacking a coherent analytical framework. While several literature reviews have been conducted to keep up with the burgeoning field of research on inequality, they often reflect the narrow focus of the literature itself. For instance, Wang and Wu (2023) examine the literature on funding inequality and Silander et al. (2021) explore the linkages between gender inequality and academic careers. These reviews tend to focus on a single or two inequalities, omitting the possibility to approach the larger structure of the system. The complexity of the subject of inequality within the research system is

insufficiently covered, especially the extent of inequality within the system, how inequality is conceptualised, and whether and/or how inequalities in research might be mutually connected beyond two components.

In this paper, I undertake a systematic review of the literature on inequality in research that encompasses the widest range of elements feasible within the scope of the study. This means that the emphasis is on the *concept* of inequality, rather than a specific inequality. It is a novel approach, yet important because concepts function as defining entities through which reality is perceived and conditioned (Lakoff & Johnson, 2008). They can be described as building blocks of thought (Fodor, 1975). How we understand inequality conceptually therefore influence how we perceive its presence in academia and its effects on the research system. The focus on conceptualisations entails a systems perspective and the study therefore also responds to academic calls that emphasise the need to view inequality in research as a structural issue (Graves et al., 2022; Rayne et al., 2023; Xie, 2014). The review is guided by the following research question:

What are the different conceptualisations of inequality in the academic research ecosystem and how are they studied?

This question is shaped by the purpose and motivation of the review (Booth et al., 2021, p. 13) which is, first, to *map* the field to elucidate the current, scattered state of knowledge and our understanding of it, but also to identify any inconsistencies or theoretical puzzles, clarifying what remains to be known. The review is intentionally exploratory and descriptive, accommodating the expected high volume of studies while maintaining analytical coherence – an important feature of the study’s design. Second, the review explores the structural interconnections between inequalities, emphasising the value in viewing the research system as an *ecosystem* in which numerous entities interact and influence each other. This challenges the prevailing tendency in the literature to examine specific dimensions of inequality in isolation. Third, the review provides critical reflections on established assumptions, norms and narratives of the field and suggests possible avenues for future research (Petticrew & Roberts, 2008, chapter 1; Kraus et al., 2022).

To the best of my knowledge, this is the first systematic review to synthesise the literature across the broader spectrum of inequality in the academic research ecosystem. The extensive body of existing research makes the review especially timely and valuable (Snyder, 2019). The review shows that inequality is a multi-faceted concept, identifying 22 distinct conceptual themes. Each conceptualisation is defined, followed by a conceptual co-occurrence map that demonstrates the interconnectedness of inequality and its structural complexity. The review also tracks temporal developments in the literature, noting a recent, steep increase in publications on the topic. This is followed by an analysis of the literature’s geographical, methodological and disciplinary orientation. The Global North is found to dominate both in terms of authorship and research focus. Quantitative methods, especially bibliometrics, are most commonly used. All disciplinary fields are represented, although most articles stem from the social sciences. Further, the review scrutinises the theoretical frameworks and explanatory models employed in the literature. It finds a lack of both theorisation and an insufficient engagement with the structural dynamics of inequality, i.e., what drives it and what effect(s) it has on the research ecosystem. Finally, the review synthesises and discusses the main findings and presents a consolidated framework to guide future research. By adopting this framework, the study provides both a foundation and inspiration for future research on the topic across scientific disciplines, as well

as a comprehensive introduction to inequality in the academic research ecosystem more broadly (Palmatier et al., 2018). Additionally, the study offers insights that may also be valuable for institutions and policy makers seeking to understand and address structural inequalities in research.

The article is structured as follows: in section 2, I outline the study's methodology, elaborating on the conceptual definitions and overall search strategy. Section 3 presents a descriptive analysis and mapping of the findings, focusing on conceptualisations of inequality, temporal developments, and geographical and methodological orientations in the literature. In section 4, I discuss the theoretical and conceptual frameworks, along with the explanatory models used to analyse structural dynamics of inequality. Finally, in section 5, I reflect on the main findings, discuss their implications and propose directions for future research, before concluding the article.

2. Methodology

2.1. Focus of the review and conceptual definitions

The review focuses on *inequality* and the *academic research ecosystem*, and I will provide a conceptual definition of both, starting with the latter. Since a key goal of this study is to encompass all possible elements of the research system the conceptual metaphor of *ecosystem* is employed. An ecosystem is defined as “a biological system composed of all the organisms found in a particular physical environment, interacting with it and with each other. Also in extended use: a complex system resembling this.” ([Oxford English Dictionary, 2025](#)).

Similar to a natural ecosystem, e.g., a forest which has living components (plants, animals, and microorganisms) and non-living components (sunlight, air, etc.) interacting in countless ways (e.g., sharing or competing for resources or utilising various processes to sustain the system), the academic research ecosystem has living components (individuals such as researchers, actors from funding bodies and journals, etc.) and non-living components (institutions, funding bodies, infrastructure, rewards, prestige, etc.) that interact in similar fashion. All components work within a joint ecosystem, sharing, but definitely also competing for resources, in interconnected and complex processes. Although similar conceptualisations exist (e.g., Lancaster et al., 2018), my approach is novel in applying this framework holistically to the academic research system as an integrated whole.

I use this definition because it effectively encompasses and captures the complexity, interconnectedness, and interdependence of the numerous, diverse components that constitute the entire academic research system. Hereafter, ‘research ecosystem’ will implicitly refer to the ‘*academic research ecosystem*’, so ‘academic’ will be omitted for brevity.

Moving to inequality, one cannot talk about inequalities in a natural ecosystem because the system is just that: natural. To describe any misalignments between components in a natural ecosystem, a more suitable definition is *imbalance*. The research ecosystem is, on the other hand, a human-induced creation. While imbalance can also exist in this system, it is also susceptible to various forms of inequalities.

Following Xi (2014), I understand inequality in research as comprising three major domains: *resources*, *research outcomes*, and *monetary or nonmonetary rewards*. Inequality in resources can refer to access (to data, journals, infrastructure, etc.), fundings and grants, etc.; inequality in research outcomes are especially related to citations and publications, but can also refer to publicity, improved networks, etc.; and inequality in monetary or nonmonetary rewards can be understood as prestige, career advancements, the ability to attract more funding and so forth. This is a useful starting point for understanding the modalities and presences of inequalities in research. It is, however, important to note that the inequalities are fluid and can easily belong to more than one of the three domains. Further, they interact with and influence each other as one would also intuitively expect that, e.g., a (non)monetary reward would have a spillover effect on future research outcomes and resources and vice versa. Inequalities can hence function as both drivers and effects. In this review, inequalities in the research ecosystem are mainly understood as of *structural* character.

2.2. Scope and inclusion and exclusion criteria

The corpus of empirical studies was identified through database searches in Web of Science (WoS) and Scopus using a meticulously developed search string (see Appendix 2). Within the boundaries and limits of this study, it was considered most efficient and feasible to employ rigorous searches in these two databases. Amalgamated, they provide a large, multidisciplinary coverage of articles and journals that is trustworthy, as well as broad in scope and time (Singh et al., 2021; Visser et al., 2021). I identified relevant keywords for block searches through an iterative and careful process (see Appendix 1). Search field was set to topic in WoS, i.e., title, abstract, keyword plus, and author keywords; and title-abs-key in Scopus as it was assessed that relevant studies would be covered by this.

A potential methodological limitation exists in the sole use of WoS and Scopus as these databases are more likely to index journals from Europe, Oceania and North America (Asubiaro et al., 2024; Mongeon & Paul-Hus, 2016). This is a methodological choice to which I acknowledge a possible inherent bias reflected in the results.

With the intention of having as high a reproduceable, well-evidenced, and transparent a methodology as possible, I applied the following criteria to define which studies to be reviewed from the database searches:

1) Only peer-reviewed articles are included. Reviews, editorials, perspectives, commentaries, letters, invited articles, opinion pieces, essays, viewpoints, books, book chapters, conference papers, and other unpublished material were excluded. This was both due to practical considerations, as the scoping searches indicated a large number of relevant studies just from the article setting, but also to only include original studies that relate to the research question. There were no restrictions on journals.

2) There were no restrictions on time, country or region. Inequality in research is no new phenomena and going back as far as possible enables analyses of historical trajectories and developments, if any. As mentioned above, there has neither been, to my knowledge, a review that encompasses inequalities in the entire research ecosystem, which further emphasises the necessity to omit time restrictions. Likewise, all countries are included to ensure full coverage on that parameter.

3) Only studies in English were included due to personal linguistic limitations, as well as it being the academic lingua franca. This might potentially introduce a minor bias to the review (or exhibit a form of inequality on its own), the non-English articles constituted a very small sample of the total results.

4) All fields and disciplines were included to ensure full coverage to the research question.

5) Studies were included irrespective of their empirical, methodological, theoretical or conceptual approaches and designs, although clinical trial studies were excluded.

6) Only studies that examine inequalities *within* the research ecosystem, defined in section 2.1., were included. Hence, articles that look at or analyse, e.g., educational inequality stemming from unequal access to higher education, were excluded because they concern inequalities that are “outside” the conceptual framework of this study. The cut-off point is from PhD level and upwards.

7) Only literature that mentioned *inequality* or *disparity* in the article, in a context related to the research ecosystem, were included. The exception being studies on *gender (gap)* and *precarial* which implicitly have inequality or disparity as a key theme (see also Appendix 1).

8) Grey literature and expert knowledge were excluded. In the face of a high volume of academic literature, the manageability of the review task was a critical concern (Adams et al., 2017). There was a limitation to resources available in terms of covering both sufficiently. I acknowledge this as a potential limitation, but omitting treading into that territory arguably helps maintain a high level of transparency, reproducibility, and systematicity (REFS?), as I avoid including cherry-picked “favourable” studies or consciously omitting “unfavourable” ones. Finally, no snowballing (i.e., forward citation or backward reference searches) were applied, following the same reasoning as the exclusion of grey literature and expert knowledge (Hiebl, 2023, p. 234-235).

This inclusivity fits the goals of the paper, as defined by the research question (Breslin and Gatrell, 2023; Rowe, 2014), ensuring the feasibility of the review and providing an authentic representation of the field.

2.3. Search and identification process

Following the PRISMA Statement on systematic reviews (Moher et al., 2009), the following strategy was employed to define my corpus of studies (Figure 1). The final searches in WoS and Scopus were conducted on January 20, 2025, yielding 4,890 studies, when duplicates were removed ($n = 2,183$). Covidence was used in all steps of the process. I first screened title and abstract, applying the inclusion and exclusion criteria from section 2.2., excluding 3,759. This provided 1,130 studies which were assessed for eligibility through a full-text screening. To reduce the risk of selection errors or bias, I was assisted by two student assistants in the process. The full-text assessment revealed another 54 studies that didn't comply with the inclusion criteria, as well as a high number of studies that had gender ($n = 738$) or intersectionality ($n = 114$) inequalities as the main focus or focal result. This was not unexpected. However, the number of articles in these two categories is too extensive for a deeper analysis within the scope of this study. While these topics are well studied (e.g., Huang et al., 2020; Kozłowski et al., 2022), I

encourage other researchers to continue exploring them, as they remain, needless to say, highly important.

Figure 1 Visualisation of the search and identification process

A total of 224 studies are included in the review (Appendix 3). They were coded by the author and the two student assistants. The coding scheme was derived abductively, focusing on the conceptualisations of inequality, as well as specifics related to *how* it is studied. The full coding scheme can be found in Appendix 4. The data was mapped and organised in Excel, while an R-code for a conceptual co-occurrence map (Figure 3) was created with ChatGPT, based on the original coded data (Appendix 5).

3. Descriptive analysis and mapping

In the following sub-sections, I outline conceptualisations of inequality, interconnections between concepts, temporal developments, and geographical, methodological and disciplinary orientation in the literature.

3.1. Conceptual analysis

The literature reveals a broad conceptual interpretation of inequality in the research ecosystem (Figure 2). A total of 550 conceptualisations of inequality was identified across the 224 included studies (the majority included more than one conceptualisation). They were grouped in 22 conceptual themes for further analysis. A synthesis of the definitions and key points of each theme is provided in Table 1.

Figure 2 Conceptualisations of inequality in the academic research ecosystem

The dominance of the concepts; publications, citations, and funding and grants, reflects a longstanding focus on these issues within the sociology of science and their high numbers were expected. All three themes are also key factors in determining success and visibility in the current research ecosystem which makes them sites of contest and inequality, as well as obvious themes of research. Additionally, they are easily quantifiable, making them manageable subjects for scrutiny. The significant mentioning of geographical inequalities signals an awareness of how the research ecosystem is disproportionately skewed toward certain regions, most notable the Global North in the form of North America and (Western) Europe. This geographical focus highlights the systemic barriers faced by researchers and institutions from the Global South. Less quantifiable concepts – e.g., hierarchies, prestige and recognition, elite(s), networks, publishing industry/business, precariat – constitute a relatively high, aggregated number as well. This suggests that researchers are aware of the multifaceted aspects of inequality within the research ecosystem. Those concepts could, however, also be considered as overlooked and insufficiently studied since their individual numbers are low in comparison to the top five themes.

Table 1 Summary of definitions and key points on how each inequality within the research ecosystem is conceptualised in the literature

Conceptualisation	Definitions and key points	Some main references
Publications	<p>Publication inequality refers to structural disparities in academic publishing across regions, institutions and disciplines. It is shaped by and deeply intertwined with factors such as language, institutional prestige, (global) geographical inequalities, and peer-review processes</p> <p>Researchers from the Global South, and non-English-speaking academics in general, face substantial barriers in the publication system. These dynamics reinforce existing hierarchies</p>	<p>Collyer, 2018</p> <p>Demeter & Goyanes, 2021</p> <p>O’Neil, 2018</p> <p>Zhang et al., 2022</p>
Citations	<p>Citation inequality means that some researchers, institutions, and regions consistently receive more citations. This often benefits already established academics, who gain further attention and recognition. Metrics and rankings amplify this advantage, making it harder for others to get cited</p> <p>As such, citation inequality is both a product and a perpetuator of broader disparities in the research ecosystem</p>	<p>Brint & Carr, 2017</p> <p>Gomez et al., 2022</p> <p>Lasco, 2023</p> <p>Nielsen & Andersen, 2021</p>
Funding and grants	<p>Inequalities in funding and grants are defined as the uneven distribution of financial resources across researchers, institutions, disciplines, and regions. These disparities are rarely isolated. Rather, they are deeply embedded in academic and structural hierarchies</p> <p>Prestigious institutions and researchers with prior success are more likely to acquire new grants, reinforcing a cycle of accumulation that advantages the already privileged. It creates a reciprocal self-perpetuating connection between various forms of inequality</p>	<p>Al Hadidi et al., 2023</p> <p>Bol et al., 2018</p> <p>Chankseliani, 2023</p> <p>Zhang et al., 2020</p>
Global North/South	<p>The Global North typically refers to the USA, Canada, Europe, Japan and Australia, with the Global South comprising the rest of the world</p> <p>In this context, inequalities are directly conceptualised through a Global North/South definition and the appertaining dynamics – a framework that, in many ways, encapsulates or intersects with all other conceptualisations of inequality in the research ecosystem</p>	<p>Demeter, 2019</p> <p>Ekdale et al., 2022</p> <p>Manky & López, 2024</p> <p>Mascarello et al., 2024</p>
Other geographical inequalities	<p>This refers to geographical inequalities that are not explicitly framed within the Global North/South divide</p> <p>Researchers and journals from less economically advantaged or peripheral regions and countries face structural barriers that, similar to the Global North/South definition, more or less comprise the scope of inequalities in this table</p>	<p>Brück, 2023</p> <p>Goyes & Skilbrei, 2024</p> <p>Huang et al., 2011</p> <p>Ogega et al., 2023</p>

Hierarchies	<p>Hierarchies in the research ecosystem are identified as multilayered structures of advantage that maintain and reproduce themselves through internal mechanisms</p> <p>They are shaped by intersecting inequalities, for example, prestige, language, geographical location and institutional affiliation, and reflected in, among others, skewed collaboration patterns and unequal research opportunities</p>	<p>Breines & Prinsloo, 2024</p> <p>Clauset et al., 2015</p> <p>Reitz, 2017</p> <p>Shen, 2023</p>
Ranking systems	<p>Ranking systems quantify academic performance through measures of universities, journals, publications, indexing databases, and other metrics. As devices of evaluation and measurement, they also function as legitimising tools that normalise existing hierarchies and practices under the guise of neutrality in numbers</p> <p>However, by fostering a constant race to climb the ranks or maintain rank, these ranking systems risk undermining egalitarian academic values and distorting research priorities</p>	<p>Bellantuono et al., 2022</p> <p>Cantwell & Taylor, 2013</p> <p>Ma, 2022</p>
Prestige, recognition and credit	<p>These concepts function as underlying levers of validation, a stamp of legitimacy, which favour the Global North and perpetuate structural inequalities. As symbolic capital, they are closely tied to, among others, institutional hierarchies, networks and ranking systems.</p>	<p>Asubiaro, 2022</p> <p>Gerhards et al., 2018</p> <p>Meyer & Zhou, 2017</p>
Language	<p>The dominance of English as the lingua franca in the research ecosystem reinforces structural inequalities. Non-English-speaking researchers face barriers in, among others, writing and publishing, while mechanisms such as rankings and journal publishing practices remain shaped by the English-language hegemony</p>	<p>Asubiaro et al., 2024</p> <p>Bhatt & Samanudi, 2022</p> <p>Marginson & Xu, 2023</p>
Publishing business/industry	<p>The publishing business of academia is dominated by relatively few Global North-based corporations. They are driven by commercial interests, not the production of knowledge, which have detrimental ripple effects on other parts of the research ecosystem, e.g., linguistic and geographical inequalities</p>	<p>Chatio et al., 2023</p> <p>Jeater, 2018</p> <p>Mills, 2024</p>
Networks	<p>Networks exist on both the individual and institutional level. They are powerful structures that shape access to opportunities, recognition, and influence</p> <p>These networks are often hierarchical and reinforce inequality by privileging elite institutions and researchers from the Global North</p>	<p>Jiang & Liu, 2020</p> <p>Landau, 2012</p> <p>Ma et al., 2015</p>
Elite(s)	<p>The share of a given “capital” – citations, funding, ‘excellence’, ‘productivity’ – is increasingly concentrated to an elite (researchers or institutions). Elite universities dominate and reproduce their advantage through e.g., funding and networks</p> <p>Several reinforcing relationships perpetuate the inequalities, e.g. various metrics, funding models and collaboration structures</p>	<p>Katz & Matter, 2020</p> <p>Orhan et al., 2024</p> <p>Parker et al., 2010</p>

Career advancement	<p>Career advancement is intertwined with and affected by networks, hierarchies, institutional prestige/rankings and lack of access</p> <p>Understanding the ramifications of these reinforcing effects are important</p>	<p>Kawa et al., 2019</p> <p>Lee et al., 2021</p> <p>Roth & McAndrew, 2018</p>
Knowledge production and epistemic inequality	<p>This refers to <i>what</i> knowledge is produced, by <i>whom</i>, <i>how</i> and for <i>which</i> purpose – all of which are shaped by entrenched power hierarchies, resulting in epistemic inequality</p> <p>These dynamics are closely connected with and influenced by other inequalities</p>	<p>Buchowski, 2022</p> <p>Demeter, 2020</p> <p>Morgan et al., 2018</p>
Academic collaboration or mobility	<p>Unequal collaboration patterns are identified, with Global North researchers typically leading, while Global South partners must make do with supportive roles</p> <p>Research mobility is similarly shaped by structural factors, favouring researchers from the Global North</p>	<p>Boampong et al., 2024</p> <p>Le Ha, 2023</p> <p>Tilley & Kalina, 2021</p>
Precariat	<p>Precarity in academia is defined as insecure, exploitative working conditions that deeply affect the lives and careers of researchers</p> <p>A significant proportion of the literature (66%) identifies neoliberalism as the primary force producing and sustaining the structures of precariousness</p>	<p>Cantrell & Palmer, 2020</p> <p>McKeown, 2022</p> <p>Smithers et al., 2023</p>
Authorship/representation	<p>This refers to structural inequalities in whose voices are included, credited, and valued in publications and collaborations – often shaped by disparities in language, geography and institutional hierarchies</p>	<p>Ekdale et al., 2022</p> <p>Hart & Perlis, 2021</p> <p>Maleka et al., 2019</p>
Open access	<p>Open access, often framed as a tool to democratise knowledge, might in fact exacerbate already existing inequalities related to publishing, access and recognition</p> <p>On a basic level, lacking resources to pay for open access reproduces traditional publishing inequalities</p>	<p>Siler & Frenken, 2020</p> <p>Siler et al., 2018</p> <p>Sotudeh & Horri, 2008</p>
Productivity/publishing	<p>Refers to disparities in how academic output is produced, disseminated, evaluated and rewarded, with structural mechanisms reinforcing these inequalities</p>	<p>Kwiek, 2018</p> <p>Lee et al., 2025</p>
Access	<p>Access to scientific literature is shaped by institutional affiliation, geographical location and infrastructural constraints, disproportionately affecting research in the Global South</p> <p>Researchers outside Europe and North America have less access to the global academic knowledge economy</p>	<p>Boudry et al., 2019</p> <p>Shanahan & Bezuidenhout, 2022</p>

Peer review process and editorial bias

Editorial bias and peer review processes often favour researchers from prestigious institutions, creating a structural barrier for certain demographics of researchers

Poulson-Ellestad et al., 2020

Sverdlichenko et al., 2022

Other

This refers to inequalities that don't fall into the other categories and occur less than five times. These are related to government policies or inequalities at the institutional level; war and conflict induced inequalities; performance and impact measures; and endowments

Bak & Kim, 2019

Hicks & Katz, 2011

McLaughlin et al., 2020

Another way of analysing how inequality is conceptualised and studied is by looking at conceptual co-occurrences. In Figure 3, the size of the blue nodes (concepts) depicts the numbers from Figure 2. The edges (lines) between each node show how often a given theme co-occurs with another concept in an article (the minimum co-occurrence is set to 2). The thicker the line, the higher the number of co-occurrences is. 53 articles analyse only one specific inequality concept, while the majority analyse inequality through at least two ($n = 72$) or three ($n = 57$) conceptual lenses. Overall, 76% of the articles contain two or more themes, indicating that inequality is most often studied as an interconnected phenomenon with tightly intertwined components.

Figure 3 Conceptual co-occurrence network map

The map reveals several noteworthy connections. Firmly centred, publications is prominent in terms of co-occurrence, occupying the top five linkages (to citations, global North/South, other geographical inequalities, funding and grants, and publishing business/industry). Publications are of crucial value to and in the academic system and its centrality and interconnections here

implies that inequality in publications is not an isolated trait. Rather, it can be influenced by other inequalities or have spillover effects on other parts of the system.

Concentrated around the centre are the other main themes – citations, funding and grants, Global North/South and other geographical inequalities – which show a strong degree of interconnectedness. The geographical and lingual inequalities are worth paying attention to as they visualise the countless ways that non-native English researchers and institutions outside dominant regions face additional structural barriers.

Language, publishing business, ranking systems, hierarchies and prestige encircle the core themes, expanding the conceptual web of connections significantly. Although they are less frequently mentioned in the literature, their relative high number of co-occurrences indicate that they are often studied in connection to other inequalities. Several of these themes also underscore how symbolic capital (e.g., prestige and status) interacts with material capital.

While there are peripheral concepts with few co-occurrences, e.g., authorship, collaboration and knowledge production in the top, mainly linked to geographical inequalities, the map illustrates the intricate network of inequalities and the dense web of interconnections between them. There are no obvious clusters, indicating that inequalities don't exist in a vacuum. Rather, the figure outlines the structural dynamics and complexity of the system.

Overall, the map shows that inequality is conceptualised as a diverse and interconnected construct, comprising numerous, often reciprocally influential notions. This interconnectedness reveals the multi-dimensional and systemic nature of inequality in the research ecosystem. It also indicates that tackling inequalities requires addressing interconnected structures, not isolated issues, as several self-reinforcing loops can be envisaged in this entrenched system.

3.2. Temporal developments

Despite having no time limitation in how far back the review went, more than half of all included studies are published within the last 5 years with an increasing tendency (Figure 4). The two early outliers are the article on cumulative advantage by Allison et al. (1982) and an article by Stephan et al. (1991) – Paula Stephan who would later publish seminal works on economics' influence on science. At the other end of the timeline, five studies already published in 2025 before the final search date in January 2025 indicate that the publication rate can be expected to continue to rise.

The recent surge could be the outcome of an increased attention to the subject of inequality in academia itself, possibly mirroring the increasing societal focus on structural inequalities in general that has gained traction over the past decade (e.g., Piketty, 2014; Milanović, 2016). Other factors are likely contributors as well, for example, an increased availability and quality of data allowing more advanced analyses of publication and citation patterns. The simple fact that the overall number of scientific publications have grown exponentially in recent years (Hanson et al., 2024), often attributed to the 'publish or perish' imperative, has possibly affected the development too. Similar, the number of publications in WoS and Scopus, within the fields of research on research, also display an upward curve, although it is less exponential than figure 4. In any case, the topic of inequality in the research ecosystem is being increasingly studied and the upward trajectory is expected to continue.

Figure 4 Publications per year

3.3. Geographical, methodological and disciplinary orientation

An important component when it comes to inequality is the geographical dispersion, as this reveals something about *what* is being studied as well as *who* studies it. Power relations and hierarchies, intentional or not, are inherently built into this distribution. Figure 5 outlines the distribution of geographical focus of the studies ($n = 256$) and the country affiliation of the articles' first author ($n = 224$). Several articles had multiple countries in focus; some had no geographical focus. 'Global' refers to studies that cover more than one continent. To simplify the figure, I piled up countries that did not figure at least 5 times in any of the two categories.

First, an important caveat must be stated. As mentioned in section 2.2., journals published in Europe, Oceania and North America are more likely to be indexed in WoS and Scopus. Combined with the exclusive inclusion of English written studies, this can have implications for the geographic trends in my data. Despite these limitations, I argue that the structural underpinnings reflected in this figure remain valuable for analysis. Finally, using first author country affiliation as a variable is not without reservations, as several nuances can be thought of related hereto. However, the large sample size, combined with the relatively low number of cross-national co-authorships, suggest that the data is still representative.

Figure 5 Geographical focus and first author affiliation

The Global North are prevalent in geographical focus and by far in first author country affiliation. First authors from the United States, Canada and European countries make up two-thirds of the sample ($n = 148$). While the geographical focus on these countries accounts for less than one third of the sample, it still represents a disproportionately high share (greater than the rest of the world). In this sense, they are both the *producers* and *subjects* of the research, creating a sort of double representation in the literature that favours North America and Europe – especially the United States. In contrast, African, Asian and Central and South American countries are underrepresented in both categories.

The literature was also coded based on the methodological approach, the authors' field or discipline, and the discipline being studied. To analyse the methodological approaches, open coding was used, which identified a total of 313 methods. While several studies utilised multiple methods, a few did not specify any clear methods. Quantitative social science methods, particularly bibliometrics, are predominant, constituting 60% ($n = 188$) of the identified methods. In comparison, qualitative methods such as interviews were only used in 7% ($n = 21$) of the studies, while case studies made up 12% ($n = 38$). Especially studies on publication or citation inequality showed a strong bias toward quantitative approaches, with only 8% employing qualitative methods. This indicates a skewed methodological distribution in that particular area of research.

As illustrated in table 2, the authors of the included literature are mainly from the social sciences, comprising 117 (41%) of the 288 identified author disciplines (see Appendix 1). This aligns with the methodological tendencies observed above. Authors from the humanities/arts represent 22%, followed by health sciences (17%), technical sciences (11%) and natural sciences (9%).

These figures can be compared with the fields studied within the literature itself. To ensure clarity, each study was assigned a single label (or none if no field was studied). Studies involving several disciplines were categorised as ‘multidisciplinary’. A total of 182 articles were coded as studying at least one field, with multidisciplinary studies making up the largest share at 46% ($n = 84$).

Table 2 Field/discipline of authors and field studied

Field/Discipline	Field of Author(s)	Field Studied
Social Sciences	117 (41%)	26 (14%)
Humanities/Arts	64 (22%)	11 (6%)
Health Sciences	50 (17%)	39 (22%)
Technical Sciences	32 (11%)	5 (3%)
Natural Sciences	25 (9%)	17 (9%)
Multidisciplinary	—	84 (46%)

The data suggests that researchers from social sciences, the humanities and the technical sciences tend to cross disciplinary fields in their studies on inequality. It is unsurprising that the majority of authors are from the social sciences given the topic of inequality in the research ecosystem. The table also indicate that inequality doesn’t recognise field boundaries. It is omnipresent, thus relevant to acknowledge across all scientific fields.

4. Theoretical frameworks and explanatory models

As shown in section 3, the literature recognises that inequality is a multidimensional concept, firmly embedded in the research ecosystem. However, identifying disparities and mapping conceptual interconnections are only a first step. A more critical and demanding task is to move beyond description to engage in theorising and studying *why* these inequalities persist, analysing underlying drivers and structural mechanisms. This section begins by examining the theoretical and conceptual frameworks present in the literature, before outlining the explanatory models used to analyse the structural dynamics of inequality within the research ecosystem.

4.1. Theoretical and conceptual frameworks

Theorisation, understood as the use of theoretical frameworks to guide empirical analysis or the in-depth application of theory to explain observed inequality, is relatively limited in the research inequality literature reviewed in this article. Of the 224 studies examined, approximately 70 to 80 engaged with theory to some extent, though the depth and function of theorisation varied considerably. While many studies focus primarily on empirical description, only a small subset explicitly use theory to frame their analysis or interpret findings in a substantive way.

However, several studies apply Bourdieu’s theory of practice (1975, 1977, 1986) to analyse specific forms of inequality. These studies are particularly valuable for their ability to ground empirical observations within a theoretical framework that enables deeper engagement with

questions of how the specific inequalities emerge and impact the field, as well as why they persist.

In these studies, the scientific field is perceived as a social field in which actors – individual researchers, institutions or other stakeholders - occupy structured positions and interact through their different forms of capital. The field is characterised by both competition and collaboration, as actors seek to maintain or improve their position using various forms of capital.

In the case of academic publishing, for example, the field is not a level playing field. The positionality of the researcher, i.e., a researcher's social position and cultural capital accumulation, has a direct influence on who are 'insiders' and 'outsiders' in the field (Arnado, 2023). Capital comes in different forms and carries different weight depending on the context. Zheng and Guo (2019) analyse how linguistic capital in the field of publishing (and the field of science on an overall level) is vital in a market where English is the dominant language. For instance, researchers with high linguistic capital, i.e., the ability to write and publish in English, can convert this capital into other forms of capital (symbolic, economic, prestigious, etc.), further reinforcing their position in the field. On the other hand, researchers with lower linguistic capital are structurally constrained in the field of publishing.

A key strength of Bourdieu's field theory is its capacity for cross-level analyses of inequality in the research ecosystem. For example, the correlation between individual or institutional capital and the larger hierarchical structures of the scientific field is found to impact the practice of researchers from the Global South (Breines & Prinsloo, 2024; Manky & López, 2024). Their response strategies to the forces of globalisation depend on the capital they possess individually. Similarly, Gerhards et al. (2018) and Papatsiba and Cohen (2019) show how the symbolic capital of an institution, or even a country, appears to affect opinions and possibilities, reinforcing inequalities on both individual and institutional levels.

Besides the Bourdieusian framework, a small number of studies analyse inequality in research through the lenses of academic capitalism and neoliberalism. Academic capitalism (Münch, 2014; Slaughter & Leslie, 1997), rooted in the broader neoliberal paradigm, theorises how universities and the broader research ecosystem have responded to neoliberal reforms and market logics. These two frameworks examine how value is increasingly assigned to knowledge and knowledge production based on economic or performance-driven metrics.

The articles emphasise how academia has become highly competitive through a marketisation process, where metrics of evaluation, various indicators, rankings and performance-based funding incrementally tighten the pressure on individual researchers, institutions and universities (Katz & Matter, 2020; Reitz, 2017). To McKeown (2022), the increased competition is reminiscent of the Hunger Games insofar as researchers compete within a game with predetermined rules: researchers must out-publish their opponents (peers) or lose the game. This corresponds to the 'publish or perish' maxim, which is also invoked in a few studies (e.g., Chatio et al., 2023). Losing the game is not simply tantamount to getting another shot at it in another round. Researchers are at risk of having to leave the profession if they don't play the game by its "new" rules – and outperform competitors. From this perspective, academic capitalism helps theorise how the research ecosystem has incorporated the neoliberal ideology to an extent that it not only creates inequalities across the system, e.g., intensifying precarious work conditions (Hari et al., 2024;

Izharuddin, 2018), but also perpetuates them through different dynamics, such as audit cultures (Soler et al., 2023)

The ‘Matthew effect’ is the most frequently applied conceptual-theoretical device in the literature, appearing in 19 of the included studies. Coined by Robert Merton (1968), referencing a Biblical verse, the term basically refers to the observation that “the rich get richer and the poor get poorer.” This colloquial reformulation makes it easily comprehensible which may partly explain its varied application across the literature. A few studies use the term only sporadically, or as a brief anecdotal reference, without integrating it into the study (Hart & Perlis, 2020; Sotudeh & Horri, 2008). Others, such as Demeter (2019) applies the Matthew effect on a macro level to conceptually frame global inequalities in scholarly productivity between the Global North and South.

More commonly, however, the Matthew effect is used as an explanatory device – a kind of conceptual travelling companion – that accompanies empirical findings rather than drives the theoretical architecture of a study. It functions as a mechanism of explanation that describes the outcomes or consequences of inequality, rather than its underlying drivers. Petersen and Penner (2014) use the Matthew effect as a reference point to describe an observed pattern of cumulative advantage and inequality in scientific careers, while Rossoni and Rosa (2024) apply it as the metaphorical yardstick to which they assess journal citation disparities and how certain mechanisms have reduced the effect. A notable exception is the highly cited article by Bol et al. (2018), who use the Matthew effect theoretically to explain how early success in acquiring funding increases the probability of receiving future funding, highlighting a causal feedback effect in academic career progression.

Juxtaposing these findings with the methodological findings in section 3.3. reveals that articles employing a Bourdieusian framework are primarily qualitative or mixed method in approach. Similarly, articles drawing on academic capitalism and/or neoliberalism also tend to follow qualitative or mixed methods. In contrast, studies using the Matthew effect as a conceptual lever are predominantly bibliometric by method. Of the 19 studies using the term, 16 employ bibliometric and/or quantitative methods. This suggests that it’s a common term within that (methodological) domain and seldomly used outside of it.

Further theoretical lenses include Cantwell and Taylor (2013), who, in their article on ranking systems and other evaluative technologies, draw on Foucault (1979; 1990) to analyse how these technologies both regulate and produce behaviour within the global research system, contributing to increased stratification among universities. Another example is Orhan et al. (2024), who in their dystopian (and satirical) paper on complete elite domination within the field of management and organisational studies use territoriality and territorial behaviour (Brown, 2009) as the theoretical basis to analyse how and why systemic issues persist, reinforce, or as their fictional story warns, culminate in perfect inequality.

4.2. Structural dynamics: drivers and effects

In reviewing the literature, I also coded explicitly for any identified structural dynamics, namely drivers of inequality and assessments of how, and to what extent, these inequalities affect the broader research ecosystem. I included both dimensions because they are equally important for

understanding inequality as a phenomenon and, crucially, because they can be interconnected and self-reinforcing.

The treatment of structural dynamics of inequality varied widely in scope and depth. Focusing first on drivers of inequality: while many articles acknowledge or briefly speculate on potential causes, only a few engage deeply and explicitly with these drivers as a central focus of analysis. Collyer (2018) provides a thorough examination of the publishing inequalities faced by academics from the Global South, identifying how mechanisms such as market concentration, commodification and monopolisation collectively drive and maintain inequalities in knowledge production on a macro level. In another study on academic hierarchies, Maesse (2017) demonstrates how technologies of rankings and discourses of “excellence” create an elitism *dispositif*, i.e., a construction of a particular positioning practice, an elite, that reinforces existing power structures of inequality in academia. Ma (2022) likewise examines how rankings and metrics have created a structural feedback loop of increasing competition and epistemic injustice that reinforce inequalities across the research ecosystem. Furthermore, studies that apply academic capitalism and/or neoliberalism in their theoretical approach also emphasise the role of *this* in driving inequalities, as touched upon above. McKeown (2022), for example, argues that the neoliberalisation of academia is the driver of inequality as neoliberal policies have permeated the scientific system and created structures of ever-increasing competition, intellectual narrow-mindedness, and detrimental conditions for academics. Similarly, studies that applied the Matthew effect naturally also identified *that* as the main driving cause of inequality, although without explaining what caused the inequality in the first instance.

Many articles, however, entirely omit analysis of any drivers of inequality, while the majority are superficial or rather rudimentary. With the latter, I refer to instances where a brief description, hypothesis, or claim is appended to an empirical finding without deeper analysis. For example, citation inequality is linked to global infrastructures of rankings and metrics (Gomez et al., 2022; Mills, 2024), to structures of power and hierarchy (Pereira, 2024) and institutionalised behaviour (Wang et al., 2022). Language disparities are found to be driven by database bias (Kim, 2024) and basic geographic affiliation (Demeter, 2020), as well as being the main driving force of inequality enhancement itself, encroaching issues of what knowledge is produced and disseminated (Marginson & Xu, 2023), as well as by whom (Ramírez-Castañeda, 2020). These studies share an implicit recognition of structural factors underlying the observed inequalities yet stop short of analysing them in depth or tracing their systemic roots.

Having examined potential drivers, I now turn to how inequalities are seen to affect the research ecosystem. Here, the pattern becomes even more pronounced: while some studies engage in thorough analysis of the potential effects of inequality, nearly half refrain from analysing or discussing the implications of inequality in any meaningful depth, offering at most a brief mention or acknowledgment of the potential effects. This may reflect methodological choices or decisions embedded within individual research designs. Yet, viewed collectively, the absence of such assessments across the literature is striking.

Among the studies that do assess the effects of inequalities, two overarching themes emerge. The first is an epistemic loss and the stifling of academia. This is commonly linked to geographical and linguistic inequalities, where knowledge and contributions by researchers from the global South are limited and structurally restricted (Cho, 2020; Sabharwal et al., 2024; Scheiner et al., 2024). Jeater (2018) shows how these inequalities expose researchers from the southern African

region with the decision to either adopt the dominant Northern research norms to achieve international publication or challenge them by creating African journals outside global rankings. Both options carry professional risk and ultimately contribute to the continued stifling of African perspectives in global academia. McKeown (2022), in her analysis of political theory research, argues that inequalities have led to epistemic degeneration to a degree, where the field is no longer about shaping political systems and seeking to change the world; rather it has evolved into a game where political scientists “aspire to score more points to stay in the game, move to the next level, or outdo their peers.” These effects are echoed by Hart and Perlis (2021), who identify that increased concentration in authorship distribution fosters academic monoculture, i.e. the inhibition of new and less accepted hypotheses that are not supported by the current establishment.

The second theme is the main effect identified in the literature. It is the perpetuation of the status quo of general inequality and/or increasing inequality and stratification. It’s an effect that crosses fields, geographical boundaries and inequality types. As such, it is easily identifiable because it serves as a common denominator in the literature, although the dividing line between effects that uphold inequality or increase them is sometimes indistinguishable. Hence, inequality in the research ecosystem is found to sustain and reinforce networks and hierarchies (Barringer et al., 2023; Liu et al., 2024) and perpetuate patterns of cumulative advantage that benefits an elite (Chan et al., 2022; Zhang et al., 2022), where assimilation is demanded if one doesn’t wish to remain marginalised (Buchowski, 2022).

In sum, the literature indicates that self-reinforcing feedback loops, in which structural drivers - such as language hegemony, rankings and metrics, institutional and geographical hierarchies – not only produce inequality, but also sustain and intensify its effects, from epistemic loss to the entrenchment of academic disparities.

5. Discussion and conclusion

This study explored how inequality in the research ecosystem is conceptualised and studied. In doing so, a descriptive analysis and mapping of the field was first provided, followed by an analysis of theoretical frameworks and explanatory models. In this section, I synthesise the main findings of the review to present a consolidated framework to guide future research. This includes identifying broad research directions and key gaps that scholars should address to progress research and understanding of inequality in the research ecosystem.

The review identified 22 conceptual themes across the literature, revealing the field’s thematic multidimensionality. This underscores the complexity of inequality in research and the importance of viewing it as more than just disparities in publications and citations – though those remain the most frequently studied indicators. Inequality also encompasses larger power structures, such as geographical location, as well as more subtle, latent power mechanisms, including social codes, norms, networks and hierarchies that exist between individuals, institutions, and nations. This basic, but not necessarily obvious, consciousness of the versatility of inequality is a decisive first step for elucidating how inequality affects research, researchers, and institutions.

Despite the complexity, the literature shows a tendency to focus on a narrow set of dominant concepts, primarily publications, citations, funding and grants, and geographical inequalities. As

such, there are apparent opportunities for further research into the less tangible forms of inequality which are crucial for understanding the full spectrum of disparities in academia. For example, the conceptual theme of prestige, recognition and credit could favourably be much further explored as it's a concept with many aspects. These are often implicit, yet they profoundly influence access to resources, visibility, and authority in science. As such, they warrant deeper theoretical and empirical investigation.

The conceptual co-occurrence mapping carried out in this paper added another layer of insight to the existing literature by demonstrating how inequality in research must be understood as a network of interrelated processes. Inequalities in academia do not exist in isolation; rather, they are overlapping and mutually reinforcing. Figure 3 illustrated the structural dynamics and complexity of the system, emphasising the value and possibilities of not only viewing the research system as an ecosystem, but also analysing it as such. However, only a small number of articles reviewed examined more than two or three inequalities simultaneously. While there may be many reasons for this, there is a great potential in adopting a more integrative, systems-oriented approach that captures how inequalities intertwine and co-evolve. Both between obvious connected inequalities, but also between less frequently connected inequalities. For example, the connection between language and ranking systems inequalities or networks and funding are promising areas for future research. While they are sparsely studied together in the included literature, their conceptual proximity and mutual association with other concepts in the network is indicative of uncharted territory where new insights can be gained. The likely increase in publications on the topic, as uncovered in the review, could be accompanied by more research on understudied inequalities and interconnections, rather than a continued emphasis on already well-established themes.

The geographical focus and first author affiliation uncovered in the literature imply that knowledge production is skewed, even on a topic that disproportionately affects the countries least represented. Inequality isn't only the subject of the research; it's embedded in the structure of the research system itself. Researchers from the Global North are in positions that not only allow them to conduct transnational research to a far larger degree than researchers from Africa, Asia and Central and South America; they can also determine *what* is being studied. While there is no inherent malice in this, it risks reinforcing structural inequalities through studying down dynamics, where more privileged countries and institutions study less resourceful ones, often without equitable collaboration (Breines & Prinsloo, 2024; Tilley & Kalina, 2021). Future research should aim to alter these structural disparities by promoting more equitable, cross-national collaboration, increasing Global South representation, and critically reflecting on how research itself may produce the inequalities it seeks to address.

Methodologically, the review highlights a strong reliance on quantitative approaches, particularly bibliometrics. While these methods are valuable for large-scale pattern detection, their dominance indicates a uniform analytical approach. This raises the question of whether the field would benefit from greater methodological diversity. Applying more qualitative and mixed methods could provide deeper contextual insights, support theory-building, and capture perspectives that are often overlooked in large-scale quantitative analyses. Similarly, the review reveals a limited application of theorisation across the literature. This is a clear gap and a missed opportunity, as studies that engage with deeper theoretical frameworks often provide valuable and critical insights to the analysis. The theoretical engagement not only sharpens conceptual clarity; it also provides more thorough explanations of the structural mechanisms and relations

by examining, among other, the underlying power dynamics and institutional logics that shape inequalities. It enables researchers to move beyond surface-level patterns to uncover why certain dynamics persist and how inequalities are reproduced. Expanding the use of theorisation could therefore significantly advance the field's analytical depth and explanatory power.

The review examined structural dynamics in the form of drivers of inequality and effects on the research ecosystem. Setting aside the studies that make no attempt to explain the drivers of inequality, the literature overall suggests that (larger) structural mechanisms are central to driving inequality. However, these dynamics often unfold across multidimensional levels, which the individual studies frequently overlook or fail to address in a meaningful way. This becomes evident with drawing aggregate inferences across the included studies. In line with the paucity in theorisation, it is problematic that so few studies thoroughly theorise on *why* the inequalities occur in the first place. Knowing what drives inequality, what causes it, is crucial for effective problem solving, be it changes of practices, policies, or a general awareness of structural mechanisms. Likewise, it is troublesome that few studies thoroughly analyse the effects inequality imposes on the research ecosystem. This lack of attention to effects is concerning: if we don't know how inequality affects the whole ecosystem, our understanding of its reach and implications remains incomplete.

Taken together, this systematic literature review suggests that existing approaches to inequality in the research ecosystem remain overly narrow in their conceptual framing. While all contributions to the study of inequality are valuable, an overly unilateral conceptualisation risks distorting and oversimplifying our understanding of the issue. Advancing the field requires not only greater conceptual depth, but also more diverse methods, stronger theoretical engagement, and more focus on both drivers and effects of inequality.

By outlining and analysing the multifaceted characteristics and features of inequality, this study makes an innovative conceptual contribution to the literature, while critically dissecting the existing body of literature. Additionally, the strength and applicability of *ecosystem* metaphor has proven valuable and warrants further use. I hope that this consolidation of the research field, alongside the identified directions for future research, will help refine our understanding of inequality in the research ecosystem. After all, how we understand inequality shapes *how* we see its implications, *what* we think needs to change, and *why* certain structures persist.

5.1. Limitations

While this systematic literature review offers a structured and transparent synthesis, it is subject to several limitations common to explorative and descriptive studies. First, the review is restricted to English-language publications indexed in two major English-dominated databases, and it excludes grey literature. This may have resulted in the omission of relevant studies published in other languages or less accessible sources. Second, the conceptual thematisation is based solely on the included studies and is not necessarily exhaustive. I encourage future research to explore other conceptualisation of inequality. Third, the review excludes studies focusing on gender and intersectionality inequalities. A systematic literature review on these important dimensions could yield valuable insights and is strongly recommended for further investigation.

Statements and declarations

Conflict of interest The author has no competing interests to declare that are relevant to the content of this article.

Funding No funding was received for conducting this study.

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Appendix

Appendix 1. Methodological considerations

Developing an adequate search string, without receiving unmanageable tens of thousands of results, was challenging. Over the course of several weeks, I continuously adjusted the keywords before I reached a saturation point where additional keywords or combinations became futile. Below, I'll elaborate on my considerations during the process.

Following numerous scoping searches, I assessed it necessary to include the term *disparity* alongside inequality because the two are often used interchangeably in studies. Including "disparity" yielded several relevant studies that were not captured when searching solely for inequality. Conversely, the concepts of "stratification", "discrimination", "(in)justice" and "inequity" were not included in the search string. While these concepts can be causes or effects of inequality too, their inclusion was deemed unnecessary as their relevance to the review's focus is limited. *Inequality* and *disparity* are primarily descriptive, whereas the latter four are explanatory, normative or moral aspects related to inequality, diverging conceptually from the scope of this review. Additionally, "unequal" was likewise not included, as it is rarely used in combination with terms which are not covered by "inequality" or "disparity".

Several forms of inequality within the academic research ecosystem were not explicitly incorporated in the search string. These include, but are not limited to, *language*, *career advancement*, *scientific recognition*, *access*, *Global North/South* and *institutional/individual networks*. Combining, for example, 'language' AND 'inequalit*' OR 'disparit*' AND 'scien*' OR 'academi*' OR 'research' in a Web of Science search provides several thousand results from which only a minuscule of articles could be relevant for this review. It would be a Herculean task with fruitless outcomes to include these forms of inequality in the search string. Most important, many concepts uncovered in the review proved to be sufficiently covered by the overall searches for inequality in research. Hence, a rather strict search string strategy was employed. Quotation marks ("") were often used to ensure that the search results only included studies where the exact word sequence appeared, e.g., "inequality in research" or "inequality in science". This was determined necessary to avoid an overwhelming and unmanageable number of results and to balance the fine line between *sensitivity* and *specificity* in my search strategy (Petticrew & Roberts, 2006, pp. 81-84). Overall, I've sought to include as many keywords as possible to cover as broad a field as possible, but at the same time set up boundaries that kept the review transparent, logical and structured.

When coding for field or discipline of the authors and the field studied, I divided disciplines into five overarching categories and labelled each study accordingly when applicable: 1) Social sciences, which include economics, law, political science, sociology, psychology, bibliometrics, scientometrics and science studies. 2) Health sciences, encompassing all medical, life and health science fields and disciplines. 3) Natural sciences, including mathematics, physics, computer science, chemistry and biology. 4) Technical sciences, such as engineering, environmental science, food and agrosience. 5) Humanities/Arts, covering information, media and communication studies, language studies and (higher) education studies. For each discipline represented by an author in a paper, one count was added. For example, if a paper had five authors all from social sciences, it counted as one for social sciences in my coding. If three

authors were from social sciences, one from health sciences, and one from natural sciences, the paper was coded as one count in each of those three categories.

Appendix 2. Search strings

Web of Science search string

(TS=("academic inequalit*" OR "inequalit* in academi*" OR "research* inequalit*" OR "inequalit* in research*" OR "inequalit* in scien*" OR "scien* inequalit*" OR "academic disparit*" OR "disparit* in academi*" OR "research* disparit*" OR "disparit* in research*" OR "disparit* in scien*" OR "scien* disparit*")) OR (TS=("citation* inequalit*" OR "citation* disparit*" OR "inequalit* in citation*" OR "disparit* in citation*")) OR (TS=(citation* OR ranking* OR tenure OR non-tenure) AND TS=(inequalit* OR disparit*) AND TS=(research OR academi* OR science))) OR (TS=("research publication*" OR "academic publication*" OR "scien* publication*" OR "research funding*" OR "scien* funding*" OR "academic funding*" OR "research grant*" OR "hierarch* in academi*" OR "hierarch* in science" OR "hierarch* in research" OR "academic hierarch*" OR "research hierarch*" OR "scien* hierarch*" OR "elite scientist*" OR "elite researcher*" OR "elite scholar*" OR "scien* elite*" OR "academic elite*" OR "research elite*" OR "scien* publishing" OR "academic publishing" OR "research publishing" OR "academic capitalism") AND TS=(inequalit* OR disparit*)) OR (TS=("academic gender inequalit*" OR "academic gender disparit*" OR "research gender inequalit*" OR "research gender disparit*" OR "scientific gender inequalit*" OR "scientific gender disparit*" OR "academic gender gap*" OR "research gender gap*" OR "scien* gender gap*") OR (TS=("gender gap") AND TS=(inequalit* OR disparit*) AND TS=("in science" OR "in research" OR "in academia"))) OR (TS=(precariat) AND TS=(scien* OR academi* OR research)))

Search publication years: no restrictions

Search field: Topic search (TS) – title, abstract, keyword plus, and author keywords

Search date: 20/1-2025

Number of results in English and as article only: **2,999**

Scopus search string

(TITLE-ABS-KEY("academic inequalit*" OR "inequalit* in academi*" OR "research* inequalit*" OR "inequalit* in research*" OR "inequalit* in scien*" OR "scien* inequalit*" OR "academic disparit*" OR "disparit* in academi*" OR "research* disparit*" OR "disparit* in research*" OR "disparit* in scien*" OR "scien* disparit*")) OR (TITLE-ABS-KEY("citation* inequalit*" OR "citation* disparit*" OR "inequalit* in citation*" OR "disparit* in citation*")) OR (TITLE-ABS-KEY(citation* OR ranking* OR tenure OR "non-tenure") AND TITLE-ABS-KEY(inequalit* OR disparit*) AND TITLE-ABS-KEY(research OR academi* OR science)) OR (TITLE-ABS-KEY("research publication*" OR "academic publication*" OR "scien* publication*" OR "research funding*" OR "scien* funding*" OR "academic funding*" OR "research grant*" OR "hierarch* in academi*" OR "hierarch* in science" OR "hierarch* in research" OR "academic hierarch*" OR "research hierarch*" OR "scien* hierarch*" OR "elite scientist*" OR "elite researcher*" OR "elite scholar*" OR "scien* elite*" OR "academic elite*" OR "research elite*" OR "scien* publishing" OR "academic publishing" OR "research publishing" OR "academic capitalism") AND TITLE-ABS-KEY(inequalit* OR disparit*)) OR (TITLE-ABS-KEY("academic gender inequalit*" OR "academic gender disparit*" OR "research gender inequalit*" OR "research gender disparit*" OR "scientific gender inequalit*" OR "scientific gender disparit*" OR "academic gender gap*" OR "research gender gap*" OR "scien* gender gap*") OR (TITLE-ABS-KEY("gender gap") AND TITLE-ABS-KEY(inequalit* OR disparit*) AND TITLE-

ABS-KEY("in science" OR "in research" OR "in academia") OR (TITLE-ABS-KEY(precariat) AND TITLE-ABS-KEY(scien* OR academi* OR research))

Search publication years: no restrictions

Search field: Topic search (TITLE-ABS-KEY) – article title, abstract, keywords

Search date: 20/1-2025

Number of results in English and as article only: **4,074**

Appendix 3. List of included articles

- Abramo, G., & D'Angelo, C. A. (2021). A bibliometric methodology to unveil territorial inequities in the scientific wealth to combat COVID-19. *Scientometrics*, 126(8), 6601-6624. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11192-021-04017-7>
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Appendix 4. Coding scheme

Following a series of test coding on both handpicked and random articles, the final coding scheme was determined. It had a focus on conceptualisations of inequality in the academic research ecosystem, as well as various dimensions of *how* it is studied in the literature.

Inequality focus/type/theme

1. Publications
2. Citations
3. Funding
4. Grants
5. Global North/South
6. Other geographical inequalities
7. Career advancement (incl. tenure and non-tenure)
8. Hierarchies
9. Elites
10. Precariat
11. Publishing business/industry
12. Ranking systems
13. Access
14. Networks
15. Language
16. Open access
17. Prestige, recognition and credit
18. Other

Geographical focus of the study

1. United States
2. United Kingdom
3. Germany
4. China
5. India
6. Brazil
7. South Africa
8. Australia
9. Global
10. Africa
11. Other

First author country affiliation

Field/discipline of author(s)

1. Health sciences
2. Natural sciences
3. Technical sciences
4. Humaniora/Arts
5. Social sciences
6. Other

Field/discipline studied

1. Health sciences
2. Natural sciences
3. Technical sciences

4. Humaniora/Arts
5. Social sciences
6. Other

Method

1. Bibliometric
2. Quantitative
3. Qualitative
4. Interviews
5. Study groups
6. Surveys
7. Case study
8. Network analysis
9. N/A
10. Other

Theoretical and/or conceptual framework

1. Bourdieuan field theory
2. Foucaultian
3. Social justice theory
4. Matthew effect
5. Academic capitalism
6. Publish or perish
7. Other

Elaboration on theoretical/conceptual framework

Drivers of inequality

Effects (of inequality) on the research ecosystem

Recommendations

Appendix 5. R-code for conceptual co-occurrence network map

```
# Load required libraries
library(tidyverse)
library(igraph)
library(ggraph)
library(readxl)

# Load your updated dataset (including the first row)
df <- read_excel(file.choose(), col_names = FALSE)
```

```

# Clean and normalize text (strip whitespace and title case)
df <- df %>%
  filter(if_any(everything(), ~ !is.na(.))) %>%
  mutate(across(everything(), ~ str_trim(str_to_title(as.character(.))))))

# Rename columns
colnames(df) <- paste0("word", 1:ncol(df))

# Pivot to long format and assign row ID
long_df <- df %>%
  mutate(row_id = row_number()) %>%
  pivot_longer(cols = starts_with("word"), names_to = "column", values_to = "word") %>%
  filter(!is.na(word))

# Count frequency of each concept (for node sizes)
node_freq <- long_df %>%
  count(word, name = "frequency")

# Create word pairs (only rows with at least 2 concepts)
word_pairs <- long_df %>%
  group_by(row_id) %>%
  summarise(words = list(unique(word)), .groups = "drop") %>%
  filter(lengths(words) >= 2) %>%
  mutate(pairs = map(words, ~ combn(.x, 2, simplify = FALSE))) %>%
  unnest(pairs) %>%
  transmute(from = map_chr(pairs, 1), to = map_chr(pairs, 2))

# Count co-occurrences and filter for weight ≥ 2
edge_freq <- word_pairs %>%
  count(from, to, name = "weight") %>%
  filter(weight >= 2)

# Create graph from edge list and node frequencies
g <- graph_from_data_frame(d = edge_freq, vertices = node_freq, directed = FALSE)

# Plot network using Kamada-Kawai layout (adjusted for new data)
ggraph(g, layout = "kk") +
  geom_edge_link(aes(width = weight), alpha = 0.5, color = "gray50") +
  geom_node_point(aes(size = frequency), color = "steelblue", alpha = 0.9) +
  geom_node_text(aes(label = name), repel = TRUE, size = 6) +

scale_size_continuous(
  name = "Concept Frequency",
  range = c(4, 14),
  breaks = c(10, 20, 40, 60)
) +

```

```
scale_edge_width(  
  name = "Co-occurrence",  
  range = c(0.3, 4),  
  breaks = c(2, 5, 10)  
) +  
  
theme_void() +  
theme(  
  legend.position = "right",  
  legend.title = element_text(size = 12, face = "bold"), # Increased font size for legend title  
  legend.text = element_text(size = 12), # Increased font size for legend text (numbers)  
  axis.text = element_blank(), # Hide axis text (numbers)  
  axis.ticks = element_blank(), # Hide axis ticks  
  axis.title = element_blank() # Hide axis titles  
)
```